

The Role of Intelligence in Dealing with the Threat of Hybrid War

Arum Wahyu Pramitasari

Defense Management Study Program, The Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia

Abstract: To deal with the threat of hybrid warfare requires good strategy and capability. One of the support capabilities needed is the role of intelligence. It is time for intelligence to look outwards and have an international outlook, to build a strong international network, in line with adopting advances in the world of intelligence and all its supporting tools. The State Intelligence Agency is the main kitchen of a government life that must be strong and successful in carrying out its programs, with great support from the people. Intelligence is the bridge that unites government and people, requiring powerful human beings who are loyal, intelligent, broad-minded, patriotic, who are willing to work tirelessly in silence. This research uses library review methods including reviewing previous references, including books and other research findings, to develop a theoretical foundation for the research subject.

Keywords: Threats, Irregular Wars, Hybrid Wars, Intelligence

I. Introductions

The environmental nature of military threats has changed as enemies and potential adversaries increasingly use nonmilitary and paramilitary means to achieve strategic and operational objectives previously considered purely military tasks. The tendency to use nonmilitary capabilities and operations to replace military force, as well as the convergence of conventional and irregular approaches, has been recognized for many years by military writers and experts. These tactics during peacetime competitions can lead to lasting negative outcomes that directly affect international security, economy, and law. There are many modern wars that can involve Indonesia. There is a proxy war, which is a war by borrowing the hands of others and there is also a hybrid war that mixes conventional war, irregular war, and cyber warfare. Hybrid warfare is a military strategy that mixes conventional warfare, irregular warfare, and cyber warfare (Tulak, 2016). In this war, by combining kinetic operations with subversive efforts, the aggressor intends to avoid attribution or retribution (Narande, 2013). Hybrid threats, among others, combine conventional, asymmetrical, terrorist and cyber warfare as well as diverse and dynamic threats (Yulivan, 2013). In addition, hybrid threats can also be a unified attack between the use of chemical, biological, nuclear and explosive weapons (CBRN-E) and information warfare (Rumekso, 2013).

To deal with the threat of hybrid warfare requires good strategy and capability. Traditional military forces generally find it difficult to respond to hybrid warfare (Budiman, 2013). Countries that are part of the collective defense system, such as NATO, may find it difficult to reach an agreement on the source of the conflict. This also creates difficulties in responding. Moreover, to counter hybrid threats, hard power is often inadequate. A much greater force is not enough to be deterrence. Often conflicts arise unnoticed, and even responses deemed "quick" prove then too late. Many traditional militaries also lack the flexibility to change tactics, priorities, and goals constantly or constantly.

One of the supporting capabilities needed to deal with Hybrid Warfare is the role of intelligence. According to Shulsky and Schmith, on an operational level, there are four essentials of intelligence, namely; (i) part of the national security system; (ii) early warning system; (iii) information management system; (iv) a system of strategic analysis, where the aim is to prevent the elimination of strategic (strategic surprises) in the field of national security and protect the integrity and sustainability of the state based on the principle of a democratic state (Bhakti, 2005). The nature of state intelligence is the first line in the national security system. The first line means being at the forefront of the national security system by providing intelligence quickly, precisely and accurately in order to maintain and maintain the sovereignty and integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. It is time for intelligence to look outwards and have an international outlook, to build a strong international network, in line with adopting advances in the world of intelligence and all its supporting tools.

The biggest challenges and threats to the country in the future are the scarcity of economic resources, mastery of information technology and competition for the quality of human resources (Rusman, 2017). Intelligence is faced with a new field of duty to provide effective Government policy materials to continuously achieve and enhance National prosperity. The State Intelligence Agency is the main kitchen of a government life that must be strong and successful in carrying out its programs, with great support from the people. Intelligence is the bridge that unites government and people, requiring powerful human beings who are loyal, intelligent, broad-minded, patriotic, who are willing to work tirelessly in silence.

II. Method

This paper uses a Literature review approach or review literature. A literature review is a research method that includes reviewing previous references, including books and other research findings, to develop a theoretical foundation for a research subject. A review of the literature in a study is useful as the basis or basis of the theory used in the research. The basis of the theory can be the results of previous research that has a similar topic or the opinion of experts who are experts in the subject we examine. The paper also conducts a literature review that is part of the literature review.

Lawrence A. Machi and Brenda T. McEvoy (2009) in *the paper The Literature Review: Six Steps to Success* explain how to conduct a library review divided into four steps. The first step is that the researcher selects or searches for library sources such as academic journals, discussing research ideas where the idea focuses on a particular topic. The second step is to identify and evaluate primary and secondary data sources that are relevant to the research topic to be studied. The third step is to develop arguments through two stages, namely a survey of the literature that has been collected and then criticalization. The final step in a library review is to write a detailed library review by identifying the themes and patterns that appear and then translated in logically arranged sections (Machi & McEvoy, 2009).

In addition, Roselle & Spray (t.t) also contributed his thoughts on the purpose and function of the existence of literature studies or literature reviews in scientific research. In literature reviews there are *question-based research projects* that have elements and processes where library reviews can help researchers in correlated between one study and another so that through the process will build a new knowledge. Then, a literature review is also useful for determining which theory is appropriate to use in solving a problem topic. This is because literature reviews can help a researcher in knowing what things have been or have not been studied, so that through this process researchers can find new problematic problems that can be further researched (Roselle & Spray, t.t).

III. Discussion

1. Understanding Intelligence

Based on law 17 of 2011 on State Intelligence, Intelligence is the knowledge, organization, and activities related to regulatory systems, national strategies, and decision-making based on the analysis of facts and data collected through operating methods for early detection and warning to prevent, prevent and counter harm to national security. In other words, State Intelligence is an intelligence organizer who is an important part of the national protection system that has the authority to regulate the functions and activities of The Nation's Intelligence. Nation Intelligence personnel are Indonesian citizens who have special intelligence capabilities and dedicate themselves to the country's Intelligence service.

The role of national intelligence is illustrated in Article 4 of Regulation No. 17 of 2011 on State Intelligence that State Intelligence performs a position in conducting efforts, work, activities and movements for early detection and early warning in the framework of prevention, prevention and countermeasures against any form of threat that can stand and threaten national and security interests.

Article 5 of Law No. 17 of 2011 on State Intelligence affirms that the purpose of the Nation's Intelligence is to find, identify, investigate, analyze, interpret and present Intelligence with the aim of providing an early caution to expect a range of real capacities and forms and trends of protection and the existence of nations and states and possibilities that exist for national interests and safety. State intelligence is the first line in the national safety system. The main line approach to be at the forefront of the national protection system by embedding intelligence quickly, quickly and appropriately to hold and maintain the sovereignty and integrity of the Unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia.

2. Intelligence Function

Intelligence has three main functions: investigation, security and enhancement. As for the explanation as follows:

a. Investigation

Investigation is the search for intelligence information through various methods, both openly and privately. The investigation is the first step in an intelligence operation to prepare for the next plan. Examples of methods of investigation include elisitation or closed-door interviews, where the questioner uses a search

for information and who is asked unknowingly provides the necessary answers. In addition, there are still several other methods in conducting the investigation process.

b. Security

Security secures data, personnel, or agencies from an attack by an opposing party. Security is one of the important elements in the success of an operation. Some methods are done in securing data one of them is to encrypt the data, so that if in the operation the other party succeeds in hacking the data but still requires a formula to decode the opening of information. In addition, the most common personnel security is to implement the use of cover in an operation.

c. Increase

Fundraising is an attempt to psychologically affect a person, many people, and society at large. Various methods are applied to create conditions in which opponents or targets become minded with the perpetrators of intelligence operations. One of the most common methods of fundraising is propaganda. This is done to contrast the opinions of opponents as opposed to the perpetrators of the operation. Propaganda itself can be spread directly (word of mouth / issues), mass media, and so on. The success rate of propaganda is one of the keys to the success of the intelligence apparatus.

3. The Role of Intelligence in Dealing with the Threat of Hybrid War

It has previously been explained that intelligence has three main functions, namely investigation, security, and fundraising. In an effort to achieve its goals, intelligence is separated to work on domestic and foreign issues. With respect to the threat of hybrid warfare, foreign intelligence should try to secure the country from war. In conducting information gathering (investigative functions), intelligence is obliged to advance and safeguard social interests in the political, economic, military, scientific, social, and security fields. In performing investigative functions, intelligence needs to strengthen three components, namely human intelligence (Humint), signal intelligence (Sigint), and image intelligence (Imint). As for the explanation as follows:

a. Humint

Humint is the intelligence capability of personnel serving in the field of intelligence. It is associated with outward abilities, such as a strong physique and an intelligent brain, as well as abilities honed with training and learning to improve insight. In anticipation of a hybrid war, intelligence personnel must strengthen. Humint's ability to get information directly to targets, such as through infiltration (spying) and so on.

b. Sigint

Sigint is the collection of information through signals, such as radio tapping, handy talky, and so on. This is indispensable for intelligence in the face of the threat of hybrid warfare. In addition to being able to fight the possibility of attacks from opponents, the intelligence apparatus can also make preparations related to the steps to be taken in the face of war. To prevent the theft of information through. Sigint, data security is necessary such as encrypting data as described earlier.

c. Imint

Imint is the process of finding information done through the collection of images/photos using electronics, infrared, ultraviolet from space, or outside photography technology. One of the most popular examples of the use of technology in Imint is the use of drones to map the situation in a region. This will be very useful in seeking information related to the strength of the opposing personnel, including the equipment prepared. For that, the search process through Imint must be done continuously to update the information. In hybrid warfare, Imint will provide information regarding the spread of the opponent's strength, so as to calculate the strength of the other party.

4. Examples of The Role of Intelligence in Dealing with Hybrid Threats

a. Information Operations in Hybrid Warfare in the European Region

Conventional hybrid warfare operations were evident in the Crimean campaign in 2014 while Russian forces successfully used psychological warfare, misdirection operations, professional internal communications, intimidation, bribery, and clean/media propaganda to weaken resistance, therefore avoiding the use of weapons pressure (Zulda, 2021). More recently, Russia's military strikes in Ukraine led former NATO Secretary General Anders Fogh Rasmussen to claim that Russia had adopted this technique (hybrid warfare), in which it is far aggregated by its well-known conventional struggles and disinformation campaigns, in addition to new, extra, state-of-the-art propaganda. In addition, it includes Russia trying to persuade public opinion through financial ties to political events within NATO and involvement in non-governmental enterprises (NGOs).

b. Information Operations in hybrid warfare in the Indo-Asia-Pacific region

In line with the Russian military, China's People's Liberation Army (PLA) has integrated hybrid war principles into a deep military doctrine called "join conventional and non-conventional action." Examples of hybrid warfare in the Indo-Asia-Pacific are shown using Chinese nonmilitary and paramilitary forces, such as Guard Beach (Coast Guard) and fishing ship enforcement, exploration oil vessels, drilling oil platforms, Commercial vessels and ship fishermen registered in China to emphasize china's still-gray territorial and maritime claims in the South China Sea. As reported by Defense News, China has shown that China is getting a number of large boat fishermen who suddenly become "maritime militias." The tactics used effectively against Taiwan in the 1990s with herd boat fishermen surrounded Taiwan's outermost islands for the Political era of tension and more recently when opposing the Philippines' deep tensions at Scarborough Shoal and when opposing Japan near the Archipelago of My Words in 2012. According to Defense News, China uses herd fishing boats to encircle disputed areas using Coast Guard Access or coerce competitors of the sea state without using military force overtly.

IV. Conclusion

The role, duties and functions of Intelligence are in accordance with Law 17 of 2011 on State Intelligence under which the State Intelligence Secretary is "a state tool that performs domestic and foreign intelligence functions, i.e. investigation, security and fundraising, whose purpose is to detect, identify, assess, analyze, interpret, and present intelligence in order to provide early warning to anticipate various forms and properties of potential and threats." Real to safety. and the existence of nations and states and the opportunities that exist in the national and security interests." Mechanically, the success of intelligence agencies in conducting analysis and providing recommendations depends largely on the assets they have. These assets are not only technical capabilities, but also individuals and networks. International networks and cooperation, intelligence agencies as an important must to work on.

Intelligence is the time to look beyond and view the international, to build a strong international network, aligned with adopting the advances of the world of Intelligence and all its supporting devices. The biggest challenges and threats of the future are the scarcity of economic resources, mastery of information technology and competition for the quality of human resources. Intelligence is faced with a new task force to provide effective Government policy materials to continue achieving and enhancing national prosperity. The State Intelligence Agency is the main kitchen of a government that must be strong and successful in implementing its programs, with great popular support. Intelligence is the bridge that unites government and people, requiring tough people who are loyal, intelligent, insightful, patriotic, who are willing to work tirelessly in silence.

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